

Unveiling the Current Extent of the Gig Economy Engagement in Developing Asian Countries

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Abstract

Background: The gig economy, driven by technological advancements, has shifted the labour market from traditional jobs to mainstream freelance and contract work via online platforms. Statistical evidence highlights the importance of examining gig economy engagement in developing Asian countries, which are key contributors to global platforms.

Objective: This study sought to systematically analyse the rise of gig economy engagement in developing Asian countries and its implications for the future of work while providing insights for platform users.

Methodology: This study was conducted in accordance with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines, drawing on past research and numerous reliable resources from 1999 to 2024.

Results: Findings reveal a growing research focus on the gig economy, particularly since 2016, with a significant increase in publications from 2019 to 2024. This highlights gaps in understanding gig workers' well-being, including stress, quality of life, and gender-specific barriers.

Conclusion: Scholars must pay adequate attention to the expanding contributions of the gig economy, considering its potential to reshape workforce dynamics and drive economic innovation.

Unique contribution: This study presents a graphical representation that illustrates the evolution of existing scholarly contributions, highlighting key gaps that require further exploration, and emphasises the vital importance of investigating this area.

Key Recommendation: Policymakers need to focus on adopting a fair work framework while addressing the underexplored areas of gig workers' experiences and challenges to foster equitable and sustainable growth of the gig economy in developing Asian countries.

Keywords: Developing Asian Countries, Employability, Gig Economy, Literature Review, Traditional Employment

Introduction

Over the past decade, research has increasingly emerged with an exclusive focus on addressing the potential consequences of digitalisation and modern technologies on typical and non-permanent employment structures by paying the way for the rise of the gig economy. The gig economy, also referred to as the open-talent economy, platform economy, sharing economy, and collaborative economy, is one of the most significant labour market transformations observed during the last decade. It is a series of flexible and less structured work opportunities that connect gig workers, employers, and customers through digital platforms (Katz & Krueger, 2017). During the 1990s, growing demand for more adaptable and flexible work schedules led to approximately 10% of the United States workforce engaging in non-permanent roles including contractors, temporary, and

on-call workers. Upwork's launch in 1999 marked a substantial development in the gig economy, fostering online connections between freelancers, especially in computer programming and information technology. By the 2010s, major gig economy platforms like Uber, Lyft, and Deliveroo emerged by radicalising outsourcing techniques which adopted a business model focusing on outsourcing minor tasks to a flexible, often precariously employed workforce that hired through temporary contracts, unpaid internships, and franchise agreements. This shift emphasises an increasing reliance on external labour markets (Katz & Krueger, 2017) over traditional employment models to hire temporary, project-based workers.

While the gig economy spans across developed, transitioning, and developing economies globally, its growth and significant contribution coming from developing countries (World Bank, 2024) which are geographically expanded within Latin America, Africa, and Asia call for specific attention. According to the Global Gig Economy Index, this region has emerged as a critical contributor to global gig work, with countries like India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and the Philippines ranked among the top ten in revenue growth (International Labour Organisation, 2020). For instance, 57.6% of Pakistan's gig earnings come from individuals aged between 25 and 34, while India, equipped with 40% of global gig jobs, stands as the second-largest market worldwide (Maciej, 2023).

Developing Asian countries have seen a significant rise in gig work compared to developed nations, but comprehensive studies on this trend are limited. This study aims to analyse the rise of gig economy engagement in developing Asian countries, focusing on its implications for the future of work and offering valuable insights for platform users. When unveiling the current extent of the gig economy engagement in developing Asian countries, this study is structured around four main objectives, which are outlined and elaborated upon in the subsequent sections. The study explores the gig economy as an emerging employment platform, emphasising its role in transforming traditional work structures and generating new opportunities. It also examines the current status of the gig economy in developing Asian countries, highlighting the trends and dynamics shaping this sector. Additionally, it explores the challenges and opportunities faced by gig workers in developing Asian countries, emphasising the factors that influence their participation and success in this evolving sector. Finally, it explores the future of gig work in developing Asian countries, examining its potential trajectory and broader implications for the region's workforce and economy.

Figure 1: Online Global Freelance Workforce

Source: OLI 2020 | onlinelabourobservatory.org

Methods

This study examines the gig economy in developing Asian countries using PRISMA guidelines. Initially, 339 records were identified through databases like Emerald Insights, ScienceDirect, and JSTOR. Reports from the World Bank, ILO, and other institutions provided statistical evidence. The search, covering 1999 to 2024, used keywords related to the gig economy and traditional employment. After excluding duplicates, irrelevant studies, and non-peer-reviewed work, 87 records met the inclusion criteria, focusing on the gig economy's current extent in developing Asian countries.

Figure 2: The Identification and Screening Processes of Literature Search

Source: Authors Compilation.

Findings from Literature

A comprehensive analysis of scholarly articles published over the decades reveals valuable insights into the evolving attention directed toward the gig economy and its key areas within this field. **Figure 3** encompasses focus areas including Labour Economics and Employment, Sociology and Well-Being, Technology and Digital Economy, Governance Regulation and Policy, and

Cultural and Geographic Perspectives along with the number of studies by year. It incorporates 87 robust studies that align with the criteria defined in **Figure 2**, specifically representing the existing piece of literature elaborated upon and utilised in this study to unveil the potential insights into the evolution of the gig economy.

From 1999 to 2006, research on Labour Economics and Employment was minimal. However, from 2016, and especially between 2019 and 2024, there was a significant increase in literature. Labour Economics and Employment within the gig economy became the main focus, with 34 studies highlighting employment patterns and economic impacts. Cultural and Geographic Perspectives also gained attention post-2019, with 17 studies exploring regional and cultural nuances.

Technology and the Digital Economy also show steady growth, especially after 2016, with 14 studies exploring the intersection and interconnection of gig work and digital transformation. Governance Regulation and Policy reveal moderate but consistent development, indicating interest in regulatory frameworks governing gig work. In contrast, Sociology and Well-Being remained underexplored, with only 12 studies by 2024. This highlights the limited focus on the social and individual impacts of gig work, aligning with Kurian and Bindu Madhavi (2024) findings which emphasise the need to address factors affecting gig workers' well-being, particularly stress, and quality of life.

Figure 3: Number of Studies by Year and Focus Area

Source: Authors Compilation.

The Gig Economy as an Employment Platform

In the latter half of the 20th century, workforce arrangements and employment structures changed significantly due to technological advancements, leading to the rise of the gig economy. Gig

workers now complete tasks directly for the marketplace, offering services to multiple companies simultaneously. This shift has transformed traditional employment structures, reorganising markets, value creation, and work arrangements. Facilitated by digital platforms, the gig economy has rapidly expanded over the past decade, moving away from traditional employer-employee relationships.

A study by Gussek and Wiesche (2024), using grounded theory examined how digital labour platforms affect freelancers' career paths, developing the 'Long-term Freelancing Career Model' to reflect career dynamics. While the gig economy aims to benefit clients and workers by providing 'on-demand' labour, platform organisations and investors are the main beneficiaries. Blyth et al. (2022) identified five self-branding strategies for freelancers on Upwork; promoting profiles, highlighting skills, expanding networks, maintaining client relationships, and differentiating their brand. The gig economy enables individuals to market their skills globally.

Gig workers must showcase their top technical and soft skills to attract clients, using IT knowledge and effective marketing strategies. Exceptional communication is crucial due to non-face-to-face interactions. Commitment and time management are key for work effectiveness. Highlighting specific skills helps attract clients quickly, allowing gig workers to establish a name in their field (Blyth et al., 2022).

Gussek and Wiesche (2024) identified three career advancement scenarios for gig workers; "Starting the advancement", "Getting credible", and "Becoming famous", shaped by platform conditions. Success requires responding to career dynamics and client uncertainties. Blyth et al. (2022) found that previous work experience, gender, reviews, and ratings are more important than educational credentials in the gig economy. Creating a profile on an online platform is sufficient without needing to upload educational certificates. Good reviews and ratings are crucial for securing well-paid gigs and achieving employment prospects.

Herrmann et al. (2023) found gender inequality in the gig economy, with female gig workers earning less than men for similar tasks, indicating a persistent gender pay gap even on online platforms where there is minimal physical interaction between workers and clients. However, the nature of gig jobs is very uncertain and challenging, requiring a stable client base for financial success. Gig workers must navigate a dynamic journey, meeting new clients, enduring the financial implications of insufficient demand, and surviving complex platform fluctuations (Vallas & Schor, 2020). High reputation scores on online platforms boost earning capacity. The gig economy offers flexibility, autonomy, and a better work-life balance compared to traditional labour markets. Gig workers are generally satisfied due to flexible work relationships and the independence of being their own boss.

Current Status of the Gig Economy in Developing Asian Countries

In today's rapidly evolving labour landscape, the distinction between traditional employment and gig work is increasingly clear. Traditional employment involves long-term, full-time roles with stable compensation and benefits like health insurance and leave. In contrast, the gig economy includes independent contractors, freelancers, and project-based workers offering services flexibly and often short-term via digital platforms (Radevsk, 2023). Once seen as supplementary, gig work has become mainstream, necessitating strategic management practices.

In the global context, Radevsk (2023) shows that 36% of the US workforce participates in the gig economy and this figure is expected to rise. In the UK, many jobs are insecure, affecting freelancers, gig workers, agency placements, Zero-Hour contracts, and part-time roles, often requiring additional support. In Poland, a study found that the temporary nature of gig work hinders unionisation, with weak relationships between workers and platforms (Polkowska, 2021). In Germany, despite global growth in freelancing, organisational mechanisms limit the expansion of platform work.

Moving to the developing Asian context, research by the Indian Council for Research on International Economic Relations (ICRIER) reveals that India has become the shelter to the second-largest market of about 15 million freelance professionals, which is approximately 40% of the total freelance jobs offered globally (Maciej, 2023). India, a developing Asian nation, is experiencing significant growth and transformation in the gig economy as the third-largest online labour market in the world. According to the Economic Times India, in 2018-2019, a notable increase in gig projects, with as many as 72% of them occurring in large corporates and professional service firms has been observed. Further, there was a heavy surge of gig workers in Delhi, with an 88% jump in six months, mainly driven by food delivery and ride-hailing platforms. Moreover, one of the survey results indicates a strong preference for freelance work, with 73% of the workers expressing a yearning for freelance opportunities over traditional full-time work arrangements (Maciej, 2023).

The Sri Lanka statistical review suggests that the gig economy is an emerging sector, particularly improved by the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic within the context of Sri Lanka. However, due to the lack of comprehensive measurement frameworks, the precise extent and nature of the gig economy remain fairly vague. The existing surveys and administrative records fall short of accurately capturing the nuances of gig work arrangements. Therefore, rigorous effort is needed to grasp its full scope and impact effectively to improve the gig economy engagement in Sri Lanka (Madadeniya, 2022). A study conducted in Indonesia shows that the key elements influencing worker engagement in the gig economy include work flexibility, work-life balance, job satisfaction, and effective stress management among gig workers. Overall, this study underlines that encouraging worker engagement within the gig economy not only boosts the satisfaction and performance of individuals but also lays the foundation for growth, innovation, and sustainability. Also, it underscores the necessity for policy implications that promote those benefits to maximise the potential of gig workers in this evolving landscape.

In Pakistan's context, digital transformation, along with globalisation, has significantly reshaped the employment landscape. In this technologically advanced world, digital platforms have become critical to access global markets and employment opportunities. Despite the challenges associated with going digital, the country uses digital connections and global economic activities to tackle unemployment and empower Pakistan's young population. However, it also underlines the necessity for strategic planning and decisive action to exploit its full potential while gaining control over its economy through globalisation's changes.

Challenges and Opportunities for Gig Workers in Developing Asian Countries

The 21st century, marked by the digital revolution and advancements in Artificial Intelligence (AI), has transformed the workforce through human-technology collaboration. Economic priorities now unite nations, with the gig economy driving industrialisation. In Asia, the gig economy has expanded sustainably, as evidenced by the Online Labour Index (OLI) from the Oxford Internet Institute, covering sectors like administrative tasks, creative work, professional services, sales and marketing, software development, and writing (Uchiyama et al., 2022).

In the contemporary labour landscape, gig workers face numerous challenges that create a bottleneck to securing quality work and being awarded fair compensation. Despite the uniform growth of gig platforms, the pursuit of quality employment is in regular form. The intense pressure from digital platforms tends to shift the heavy burden onto the shoulders of gig workers while leading to their psychological imbalance. This hassle can negatively affect the quality of service provided to customers by further intensifying the situation of the gig worker (Jamshedpur et al., 2023). Moreover, employers are embracing the latest technological advancements to monitor and extract surplus work from gig workers, resulting in work overtime and increased stress levels. This exploitation by firms in the gig economy exposes gig workers to uncertainty and inequality and drags them at systemic risk as a whole. Indeed, gig workers face inequality and discrimination based on gender and race, leading to stagnant wages and a widening income gap among workers (Joshi et al., 2024). This provides evidence that the dynamic contributes significantly to the rising wage inequality in the gig economy (Uchiyama et al., 2022). The gig labour market emphasises economic challenges for gig workers and provides critical exposure to income inequality and exploitation in modern employment paradigms.

On the other hand, technological advancements have brought challenges to the gig economy, such as digital fatigue, which blurs work-life boundaries and increases stress. Ensuring sustainability is crucial. The gig economy has led to informalisation in developed countries, characterised by low wages and poor social protection, and the situation is worse in developing countries. Disparities in services and access to digital technology, especially in rural areas, limit participation in the gig economy, which is mainly urban. These issues exacerbate inequality and create barriers for workers in these regions (Uchiyama et al., 2022).

Today gig workers have to face unforeseen futures with the persistent threats of termination and deprived of essential social security benefits like Employees' State Insurance (ESI), and Employees' Provident Fund (EPF), exposing them to financial instability (Joshi et al., 2024). As per the example, In India, the gig economy emphasises the challenges of an unregulated informal work sector with inadequate safeguards for social security and insurance (Jamshedpur et al., 2023). The precarious economic situation of these workers is further exacerbated by the fact that they typically work in substandard conditions and face issues with payment security. When it comes to the practical scenarios of gig work, there are still unresolved issues regarding skill acquisition and career development as demonstrated by studies comparing job application response rates among different groups. Platforms like Amazon Mechanical Turk and Upwork exacerbate common challenges faced by gig workers, making their career paths even more complex. The ample of job alternatives in the gig economy makes workers uncertain about their future, which will pave the way to demotivation and dissatisfaction evident among gig workers. Further, inadequate training

is provided by employers regarding the assigned tasks and employees need to fulfil the required training and education through their experiments and learnings to adapt to the dynamic nature of gig work. Gig workers face a stimulating landscape, including financial insecurity and career ambiguity, while succeeding there requires resilience and sustained learning.

Gig work is often characterised by a transient nature that leaves a vacuum for career advancement and skill enhancement, which obstructs long-term career planning and constrains opportunities for professional development. Further, it challenges workers with skills alignment, career development, and employment guarantee. This issue underlines the requirement for a regulatory framework to protect workers' rights and well-being, and the gig labour landscape challenging traditional labour standards. The lack of a clear designation of gig workers in current legal frameworks exacerbates these challenges, emphasising the need for change (Jamshedpur et al., 2023). Policymakers, law enforcement authorities, and institutional decision-makers have the authority to establish steps to protect gig workers, who currently have limited job security and benefits due to a lack of regulation.

Technological advancements have transformed labour markets, fostered the gig economy, and reshaped the traditional education-income model. In many developing Asian countries, gig work is popular for supplementary income (Herrmann et al., 2023). Gig workers demonstrate adaptability and diverse skills, enhancing innovation and competitiveness. The gig economy also includes disabled workers, breaking traditional workplace boundaries. Digital labour platforms provide global access to an on-demand workforce, allowing independent contractors to expand their services nationally and internationally, reducing costs through platforms like Uber and Airbnb.

When considering the Sri Lankan context there are a limited number of studies that have been conducted so far regarding the concept of gig work. However, a study conducted by Priyankara (2021) has examined the gig economy in Sri Lanka in terms of gig work nature, operations, attractions, and criticisms from the actor's perspective and reviews the challenges and opportunities. Further, the study states that Sri Lanka is facing a significant challenge in controlling non-local gig platforms since most of the gig platforms are based in developed countries which causes an inability to capture the value additions through those platforms and results a potential tax earning losses for the government.

Further, the gig economy enables people to become entrepreneurs and gain financial benefits by leveraging their unique skills and allowing them autonomy and flexibility as independent contractors and freelancers (Myhill et al., 2021). This promotes not only the sense of empowerment, but also improves motivation, job satisfaction, and financial independence. Additionally, it facilitates a better work-life balance allowing workers to personalise their work schedules and integrate personal and professional duties efficiently and offer greater control over their lives (Kurian & Bindu Madhavi, 2024). Besides, the gig economy stands as a giant pillar of creating a vast range of employment options and provides the chance for upgrading skills and specialist diversification to meet evolving market demand by offering a wide range of employment opportunities globally in contrast to traditional employment options that are limited to local or regional constraints.

Future of Gig Work in Developing Asian Countries

The gig economy is on the rise and is expected to continue growing in upcoming years in the UK (Radevsk, 2023) and the US. Gig platforms could provide crucial employment opportunities to tackle unemployment, especially for the youth. In the context of developing Asian countries, the gig economy has accompanied substantial contributions, specifically from India. It accounts for 24% of gig workers worldwide, making it the second-largest freelancer market globally with 15 million specialists (Maciej, 2023). Furthermore, by 2018, it had become the fifth-largest nation in terms of flexible staffing, with 3 million gig workers. Consequently, according to the Global Gig Economy Index, four countries from the Asian context India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and the Philippines are included in the top ten in revenue growth. Despite their contribution, developing Asian countries are far behind in developing employment standards for gig platforms and employee well-being.

Improving security and work quality for job seekers and providers requires setting minimum employment conditions. The “Fair Work Framework” (Heeks et al., 2021) can enhance gig workers' conditions, allowing Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and investors to certify platforms with fair standards and educate gig workers about these conditions (Ayentimi et al., 2023). Consequently, establishing appropriate job standards in informal settings is very crucial. Moreover, there is a need to identify the facts that affect well-being since it is affected by stress and the quality of life of gig workers (Kurian & Bindu Madhavi, 2024).

It is evident that existing literature has fallen short of examining the gig workers' motivations and experience (Ayentimi et al., 2023; Myhill et al., 2021) and the challenges faced. Further research must focus on evaluating these components on major gig platforms such as Upwork, Freelancer, Fiverr, and Uber, particularly in countries like India, Sri Lanka, Bangladesh, and Pakistan. This evaluation can help identify areas for improvement and inform platform users and policymakers. Post-evaluation, findings should be employed in gig platforms, incorporating certification and registration systems to standardise work practices. Moreover, exploring how gig workers can leverage social media and review systems to identify platforms with fair work standards is crucial (Ayentimi et al., 2023).

Gig work was once supplementary but now is a primary income source for many in regions with rising unemployment. Digital labour platforms, especially post-COVID-19, offered more opportunities, encouraged innovation, and reduced gender gaps in employment. Moreover, female participation in the region is comparatively lower (Datta & Chen, 2023) than in other regions due to the cultural and social barriers which indicate a significant drawback of particular workers refraining from utilising their skills. Gig workers face challenges in collective representation due to their self-employment status and the lack of traditional governance systems (Ayentimi et al., 2023). Those informal economic conditions limit crowd workers' collective voice. However, social media and community networks can enhance collective organisation and support for gig workers (Ayentimi et al., 2023).

Understanding the engagement of Gen-Z in the gig economy, particularly university undergraduates, is vital as they represent the future workforce. However, there is a vacuum in

exploring the experiences and challenges of the particular context which has become challenging for policymakers to identify employment landscape behaviour. Moreover, Kurian and Bindu Madhavi (2024) suggest that conducting studies employing a larger sample and a wider range of geographical representations will assist in understanding gig worker behaviour and how gig worker characteristics change over time.

Conclusion

The gig economy is an integral part of the new global workforce, providing immense employment opportunities and economic contributions, especially for developing Asian countries. India is a notable example, with a considerable share of the global gig workforce. Given the importance of continuously exploring the dynamics of gig work, the study outlines its limitations and offers actionable recommendations derived from the findings of the study.

Regardless of the significant findings of the study, there are certain limitations to consider. For instance, the study is limited in its spread among a wider range of gig workers as it especially provides attention to gig workers who are from developing Asian countries. Also, as the study focuses on aggregating and synthesising evidence, it lacks capturing context-specific insights or nuanced interpretations that are unique to individual studies potentially limiting its depth. Additionally, this study reflects a snapshot of research available at the time of the review, making its findings susceptible to becoming outdated as new studies emerge. Moreover, database limitations and restricted access to paywalled articles may have excluded the other relevant studies, potentially impacting the results and conclusions of the study.

In this respect, it is quite urgent to have in place frameworks like the "Fair Work Framework" to help improve the working conditions for gig workers, including minimum employment standards, certification of fair practices, and educating workers about labour rights. Employers and gig platforms should enhance worker benefits by providing health insurance, retirement plans, and paid leave to improve overall well-being. Implementing transparent policies in payment structures, job expectations, and performance evaluations is crucial to building trust and fairness.

The findings of the study highlight that despite the growing body of literature on gig work, governance regulations, and policy-related research in this area remain significantly underexplored. While existing studies address regulatory challenges, social protection, and fair work standards, they primarily highlight issues rather than proposing comprehensive solutions. Future research should focus on developing robust governance models and policy frameworks to address labour rights, social security, and fair work standards, ensuring equitable and sustainable conditions for gig workers. Additionally, researchers and academics should expand their focus on the social and psychological impacts of gig work, including stress, job satisfaction, and quality of life. Investigating how gig work varies across regions and cultures can help develop tailored solutions.

Moreover, further research should focus on understanding gig workers' motivations, experiences, and challenges, especially on major platforms like Upwork, Freelancer, Fiverr, and Uber in the aforementioned region. Besides that, clarity on the role of Gen-Z concerning the gig economy and addressing these cultural and social barriers that act as stumbling blocks to further participation by

females are considered important for sustainable growth within this sector. Improvements in collective representation through digital and community networks can contribute to overcoming the limitations set by the informal nature of the economy that gig workers face. Continuous evaluation and adaptation of employment standards will be of utmost importance if the gig economy is to grow in an equitable and just manner.

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